

An open forum to explore science policy topics more deeply and drive for change

Founded in 2020 by Shahid Hanif and Annette Schmid, the Science Policy Think Tank was established as an **open** and **independent forum** for **thoughtful deliberation** of key issues and appropriate action in science policy as it relates to accelerating innovation for the benefit of patients that results in a strong and influential voice for its members.

Importantly, the forum and discussions are intended to focus on subject matters of relevance and impact and reflect a balance of all stakeholder interests.

Mission:

Bringing together a **diverse group of members** with interest in science policy as it relates to accelerating innovation for the benefit of patients.

- To determine and **share intelligence** of the challenges, opportunities and potential gaps
- To **learn and build** on different perspectives
- To focus discussions and efforts on subject matters of relevance and impact that reflect a balance of all stakeholder interests
- To understand whether these **issues are being addressed** appropriately by stakeholders or would benefit from our action

Founding Members and Steering Committee

The group was founded with the coming together of individuals from academia, non-for profits, pharma, biotech and independent consultants with an interest in advancing Science Policy.

The Steering Committee, working on the Biospecimens Open Forum, currently includes (in alphabetical order):

Virginia Acha, DPhil Merck, Sharp and Dohme (UK)

Read more about Virginia on her [LinkedIn](#) profile

Barbara Bierer, MD, MRCT Brigham and Women's Hospital & Harvard University (US)

Read more about Barbara on her [LinkedIn](#) profile

Eleanor Dehoney, MSc, ResearchAmerica (USA)

Read more about Ellie via her [LinkedIn](#) page

Jon Fistein, MB BChir Private Healthcare Information Network (UK)

Read more about Jon on his [LinkedIn](#) profile

Shahid Hanif, PhD Avenzoar Consulting, (Canada)

You can read more about Shahid via [LinkedIn](#)

Wohaib Hasan, PhD, Takeda (USA)

Learn more about Wohaib here: [LinkedIn](#)

Namir Hassan, DPhil, Zelluna Immunotherapies (UK)

Read more about Namir on his [LinkedIn](#) profile

Mayumi Kusunose, MBE, MA, Riken Institute (Japan)

Read more about Mayumi on her [LinkedIn](#) profile

Gabriela Lavezzari, PhD, MBA, GSK (USA)

Find out more about Gabriela here: [LinkedIn](#)

Annette Schmid, PhD, Takeda (USA)

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